
Technical Report

Report on system topology and control options, and model development for energy hubs

Deliverable 2.1

November 30, 2023

This report forms part of the DIRECTIONS project, funded by the Energy Transition Funds, FOD Economy, Belgium.

Report editor: Dr. ir. Özgür Can Sakinci, Prof. dr. ir. Jef Beerten

Authors and contributors: Dr. Thomas Roose, Ir. Francisco Javier Cifuentes Garcia, Dongyeong Lee, Jan Kircheis
Under the supervision of Prof. dr. ir. Jef Beerten

Contents

Executive Summary	4
1 Energy Hub Topologies and Control Options	5
1.1 Energy Hubs: Definition and Topological Alternatives	5
1.1.1 Definition	5
1.1.2 System Topologies	6
1.2 Control of an energy hub	7
1.2.1 The need for grid-forming control	8
1.2.2 Review of different grid-forming control options	8
1.3 Conclusion	9
2 Model Development for Energy Hubs	10
2.1 Multi-Terminal Impedance-based Stability Analysis	10
2.1.1 Impedance-based stability analysis by separation of system in node and edge subsystems	11
2.1.2 System oscillation mode and participation factor analysis	12
2.2 Transmission Line Modeling	13
2.3 Converter Modeling	14
2.4 Offshore Wind Farm Modeling	14
2.4.1 Grid-Following Wind Turbine Model	14
2.4.2 Simplified Wind Farm Model for System-Wide Stability Analysis	15
2.5 Automated Subsystem Identification in the Frequency Domain	17
2.5.1 Generalities of the identification procedure	18
2.5.2 Admittance identification of sources and loads	19
2.5.3 Admittance identification of converters	19
2.5.4 Admittance identification of AC and DC networks	19
2.6 Conclusion	20

Executive summary

This report presents the first deliverable in the DIRECTIONS project for WP2, which applies to Tasks 2.1 and 2.2.

The first chapter discusses topologies and control options for energy hubs. Topological alternatives utilizing different forms of interconnections based on AC and/or DC technology are introduced, and the particular control-related challenges associated with the different alternatives are highlighted. The presence of parallel AC and DC connections in close proximity is identified as an important factor increasing the risk of control interactions, in addition to the low system strength in an offshore network composed entirely of power electronics. The aiding role played by novel grid-forming controllers is mentioned as a critical feature of energy hubs, and conditions where grid-forming control is a necessity are discussed. The chapter concludes with a brief overview of different grid-forming control options that are available in the literature, which all provide the same desired functionalities through different designs.

The second chapter covers the modeling of energy hubs. Following a brief introduction of the fundamental principles behind impedance-based multi-terminal stability analysis, guidelines are given for the modeling of crucial energy hub components, i.e., transmission lines, converters and offshore wind farms. Modeling simplifications are provided for bundled subsea cables and offshore wind farms. Particularly for the offshore wind farm case, it is demonstrated that depending on the specific modulation strategy considered by the converters, a Type IV wind turbine can be represented solely by its grid-side converter. The chapter is concluded with the introduction of a novel frequency scanning tool developed in Python, which can efficiently derive impedance/admittance transfer functions for potential black-boxed models in EMT software.

1

Energy Hub Topologies and Control Options

This chapter provides a brief overview on topologies and control options for energy hubs. Following a brief discussion on energy hub definitions and topological alternatives, control options for energy hubs are introduced, and the specific role of grid-forming control is explained. Finally, the chapter concludes with a review of different grid-forming control architectures that have so far been proposed in the literature.

1.1 Energy Hubs: Definition and Topological Alternatives

1.1.1 Definition

Many definitions exist in the literature for the energy hub concept. In one of the early works from 2007, an energy hub is defined as “a unit where multiple energy carriers can be converted, conditioned, and stored” [1]. In this definition, an energy hub acts as a coupler for multiple energy carriers (such as electricity and natural gas). The specific aspects (such as energy conversion and storage) of energy hubs fitting this initial definition have been well studied [2].

With the ever-increasing importance of energy transition and the significant role played by offshore wind, an alternative energy hub concept has recently emerged in the context of energy islands. An energy island can be defined as “a hub connecting multiple offshore wind power plants to the power grid using multiple HVDC converters from different vendors”, and they can “also host storage and power-to-gas conversion units” [3]. Motivated by the proposed definition, an energy hub can be seen as an interconnecting unit in the transmission infrastructure, where the key role is the facilitation of the integration of offshore wind power. A similar feature is also noticed in the North Sea Wind Power Hub project, where the focus lies on the collection of offshore wind power in a “hub” to which multiple countries are connected [4].

Overall, the following aspects are identified while defining energy hubs in the context of DIRECTIONS:

- Allowing bulk renewable integration

- Connecting multiple zones using (hybrid) interconnectors

1.1.2 System Topologies

In line with the aspects explained in the previous section, a test network was built in WP2 in order to analyze potential control-related challenges that can be observed in energy hubs. The single-line diagram of the proposed test network is depicted in Fig. 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Single-line diagram of the energy hub test network.

The network topology in Fig. 1.1 covers the essential aspects mentioned above, i.e., the network integrates offshore wind power and connects two AC zones (represented using infinite buses at AC buses g1 and g3) using a combination of AC and DC interconnectors. In addition to the full version depicted in Fig. 1.1, three alternative topologies will be investigated in this work package, which independently focus on specific control-related aspects that can be observed in energy hubs. These topologies gradually lead up to the fully hybrid topology in Fig. 1.1, and are explained next.

Topology I: AC Only

In this alternative energy hub topology depicted in Fig. 1.2 the offshore wind farm (OWF) is connected to the onshore network through an AC cable, and no HVDC links are present in the vicinity of the energy hub. This topology, by nature, does not allow for the interconnection of multiple zones due to the absence of DC links given the infeasibility of using long subsea cables for AC connections. The main control challenge in this scheme will be voltage control and reactive power compensation in a connection based on an AC cable.

Figure 1.2: Alternative topology I with an AC connection of the OWF only.

Topology II: AC & DC, No Interconnection

This topological alternative shown in Fig. 1.3 presents unique control challenges, as it involves an AC cable in parallel with an HVDC link. In addition to the problems related to voltage control mentioned for Topology I, unique

problems related to HVDC control are expected in this topology due to the low frequencies of network resonances at the AC terminals of the HVDC link and the potential couplings through the parallel DC connection.

Figure 1.3: Alternative topology II with parallel AC and DC OWF connections.

Topology III: DC Only

Topology III presented in Fig. 1.4 is a DC-only solution for the integration of offshore wind power and is unique in the sense that grid-forming control (to be explained in detail in the following section) has to be considered for the OWF. The responsibility of forming an AC voltage offshore can either be taken up by the HVDC link or the OWF itself.

Figure 1.4: Alternative topology III with a DC connection of the OWF only.

1.2 Control of an energy hub

Since energy hubs are a novel technology and have not been built yet, no state-of-the-art control strategy for this kind of power system exists. However, it is already apparent from the energy hub concept that novel, innovative solutions for power system control are needed to operate energy hubs in a safe and stable manner. The high density of power electronic converters will result in a power system with low to zero inertia and low short-circuit power. Moreover, given that energy hubs will be mostly built at remote locations far away from strong grid connection points, energy hub networks can be classified as weak connections. Another essential characteristic of an energy hub power system is potential converter control interactions that can be observed between the core components of the energy hub (i.e., converters and auxiliaries) themselves and between the core components and the AC/DC grid. Furthermore, energy hubs might combine converters from different manufacturers, rendering the stability analysis difficult due to intellectual property (IP) issues. In addition, energy hubs will operate semi-independently from the main power system with the additional functionality of operating independently during black start operation, further complicating controller design.

1.2.1 The need for grid-forming control

As discussed above, one of the salient electrical characteristics of energy hubs is the hub's weak power system, which is the outcome of the electrical remote location on the one hand and the high density of converter-interfaced assets on the other hand. This uniqueness requires a suitable control strategy for the energy hub to ensure the safe and reliable operation of the hub's power system. In this case, grid-forming control of converters could be employed to cope with the specific challenges of a weak power system. Grid-forming control strategies have been attracting considerable interest from the power system community in recent years and are thought to be a cornerstone of a future power system with high penetration of converters. In contrast to standard grid-following converters that behave as controlled current sources, grid-forming converters can be conceptualized as controlled voltage sources behind an impedance [5]. This voltage source behavior also becomes a necessity for DC-connected wind farms, as a voltage has to be formed for the AC collection network inside OWFs. With this altered control paradigm, grid-forming converters are capable of providing additional functionalities that enable this control strategy for the operation in weak power systems. Supporting functionalities that grid-forming converters can provide are [6]:

- Voltage source behavior
- Voltage and frequency support
- Blackstart capability

While voltage and frequency support can also be provided by grid-following converters, the intrinsic current source behavior of grid-following converters is completely opposed to the desired voltage source behavior of generation units in weak grids [5]. Grid-forming converters are able to provide instantaneous response to grid events, such as faults, voltage swells/sags and angle jumps. In addition, the intrinsic voltage source behavior of grid-forming converters provides the required voltage signal for grid-following converters in order to operate. Since grid-following converters do not establish a voltage signal themselves, they require a stable AC voltage in order to synchronize with the network and inject active and reactive power [5].

The main characteristics identified above for grid-forming control can be provided by different implementations. In the following, an overview will be given of different grid-forming control philosophies that have hitherto been proposed in the literature.

1.2.2 Review of different grid-forming control options

In the following, common grid-forming control strategies are reviewed. In a traditional cascaded control structure, typical grid-forming control schemes consist of outer control loops that generate the reference for the required voltage phasor $V_{GFM}\angle\theta$ and inner loops that manipulate the converter's voltages and currents to track the reference voltage. For the sake of brevity, only the outer control loops are reviewed here.

In transmission systems the impedances are mostly inductive (i.e., $R \ll X$). This means that the control of active power is mainly linked to the control of angles, and the control of reactive power to the control of voltage magnitudes. Hence, the outer control loop is further differentiated into an active power control loop manipulating the angle of the voltage phasor $\angle\theta$ and into a reactive power control loop manipulating the magnitude of the voltage phasor V_{GFM} .

Active power control

A wide range of active power control schemes for grid-forming units have been proposed in the literature. A control approach initially designed for HVDC applications is the power synchronization control [7]. This control strategy aims at emulating the synchronization mechanism of synchronous generators, and it was initially designed for HVDC transmission systems in weak grids [7]. The following equation describes the control strategy:

$$s\Delta\theta = K_{p,syn}(P_{ref} - P), \quad (1.1)$$

where $K_{p,syn}$ is the gain, P_{ref} is the active power reference and P is the measured active power injected into the grid. For initial synchronization with the power system and during faults a backup PLL is usually employed [7].

Another well-established active power control scheme that has its origins in microgrids is droop control, which can be described by the following equation [8]:

$$\omega = \omega_{ref} + D(P_{ref} - P), \quad (1.2)$$

where ω is the frequency of the grid-forming unit, ω_{ref} is the fundamental grid frequency and D is the droop coefficient. The measured active power P is normally low-pass filtered not only to reject disturbances and measuring noise, but also to improve the stability of this control scheme [9].

One more mature active power control technique for grid-forming units is the virtual synchronous machine strategy that mimics the behavior of synchronous generators [9, 10]. For that control strategy, different implementations with varying levels of accuracy exist. However, the emulation of the swing equation of a synchronous generator is at the core of all implementations [9]. Consequently, the active power control loop of a virtual synchronous machine can be generalized to:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{s} \frac{1}{2H} [(P_{ref} - P) - k_d (\omega - \omega_{grid})], \quad (1.3)$$

where H is the virtual inertia, ω_{grid} is the grid frequency and k_d is damping coefficient.

Reactive Power Control

So far the reviewed control schemes control the active power by manipulating the angle of the converter's voltage phasor. Additional outer control loops are commonly employed to control reactive power by manipulating the magnitude of the voltage phasor. Different implementations exist for that purpose, yet compared to the active power control loops only slight variations across various reactive power control implementations can be observed [5]. Typically, the reactive power control loop has the general form as follows:

$$V_{GFM} = K_{p,q} + \frac{K_{i,q}}{s} (Q_{ref} - Q) + V_{ref}, \quad (1.4)$$

where $K_{p,q}$ is the proportional gain of the controller, $K_{i,q}$ is the integral gain, Q_{ref} is the active power reference, V_{ref} is the voltage magnitude reference and Q is the measured reactive power injected into the grid. A PI controller is used to achieve zero error in steady state.

1.3 Conclusion

This chapter introduced the concept of energy hubs and discussed topological alternatives as well as control options. Bulk renewable integration and the connection of multiple zones using hybrid interconnectors were distinguished as key features of energy hubs. A test network to be used in WP2 was introduced, and various topological alternatives focusing on different control-related challenges were illustrated. The chapter concluded with a discussion on the need for grid-forming control, and explained the alternatives proposed in the literature that can achieve the desired functionalities through different control approaches for the regulation of active and reactive power transfer.

2

Model Development for Energy Hubs

In this chapter, details are provided on the modeling assumptions to be taken while building energy hub models for small-signal stability studies, which are the main focus of WP2. After introducing the fundamentals of impedance-based small-signal stability analysis, details are given on the modeling of important system components, i.e., transmission lines, power electronic converters, and offshore wind farms. The models are developed in the in-house impedance-based stability analysis tool HVDCstability.jl, which makes use of two-port representations of individual power system components (as depicted in Fig. 2.1) to arrive at models that are accurate over an extended frequency range [11]. The chapter is concluded with the introduction of an automated frequency scanning tool developed within the project, which forms an integral part of small-signal studies involving black-box component models.

Figure 2.1: Two-port representation of power system components.

2.1 Multi-Terminal Impedance-based Stability Analysis

A general representation of a hybrid AC/DC energy hub, where AC and DC networks are interconnected through multiple converters, is shown in Fig. 2.2. An energy hub can contain converters and other equipment provided by multiple vendors, limiting the information available on these components due to confidentiality reasons. Using the impedance-based method enables performing small-signal stability analysis of the system based on black-box models [12]. The classical use of this method relies on the separation of the system at a single terminal into

source and load subsystems, represented by their small-signal impedances $Z_s(s)$ and $Z_l(s)$ respectively. The variable s indicates the Laplace operator. These subsystems form a closed-loop system with loop gain $L(s) = Z_s(s)Z_l^{-1}(s)$ whose stability can be assessed by evaluating the Nyquist plot of $L(s)$ using the Generalized Nyquist Criterion (GNC) [13].

Figure 2.2: General representation of hybrid AC/DC energy hub. Definition of node (converters, sources and loads) and edge (DC and AC network) subsystem.

However, this approach may lead to an incorrect stability assessment in the case of systems with multiple converters, e.g. energy hubs. The impedance-based method assumes that the two subsystems are individually stable since the stability can then be determined by checking whether the $(-1, 0j)$ point in the Nyquist plot is encircled (unstable) or not (stable). If multiple converters and other system components are aggregated in the source or load subsystem, this possibly causes subsystem instability due to adverse converter-related interactions [14]. To have an accurate stability assessment in this case, the number of right-half plane (RHP) poles of $L(s)$ needs to be known. This requires an analytical representation of the system, preventing the use of black-box models. To solve this issue, an alternative impedance-based method is proposed here, allowing to perform an accurate stability assessment of hybrid AC/DC energy hubs using black-box models.

2.1.1 Impedance-based stability analysis by separation of system in node and edge subsystems

Contrary to the classical use of the impedance-based method, where the system is separated at a single terminal into source and load subsystems, node and edge subsystems are now defined at multiple terminals. This approach is depicted in Fig. 2.2. The node subsystem (gray area) contains the converters, sources, and loads of the energy hub, which are connected at particular nodes. These nodes are interconnected through the DC and AC networks, which are combined in the edge subsystem (white area). Subsequently, the small-signal stability of the energy hub can be assessed based on the closed-loop interaction of the node and edge subsystems.

The edge subsystem is represented by the edge impedance matrix $Z_{edge}(s)$, giving the relation between the node voltages and current, i.e ΔV and ΔI respectively,

$$\Delta V = Z_{edge}(s)\Delta I. \quad (2.1)$$

Vectors and matrices are noted in bold italic, and Δ indicates small-signal perturbations of the variables. The voltages and currents at the terminals of the n converters and m sources/loads, distinguished by the subscript g , are:

$$\Delta V = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta v_1^T \cdots \Delta v_n^T & \Delta v_{g1}^T \cdots \Delta v_{gm}^T \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (2.2a)$$

$$\Delta I = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta i_1^T \cdots \Delta i_n^T & \Delta i_{g1}^T \cdots \Delta i_{gm}^T \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (2.2b)$$

The superscript T denotes non-conjugate transposition. In addition, the converters and sources/loads are modeled by their Norton equivalent [15],

$$\Delta I = \Delta I_N - Y_{node}(s)\Delta V, \quad (2.3)$$

where I_N represents current disturbances at the nodes,

$$\Delta I_N = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta i_{N,1}^T \cdots \Delta i_{N,n}^T & \Delta i_{N,g1}^T \cdots \Delta i_{N,gm}^T \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (2.4)$$

The node admittance matrix $\mathbf{Y}_{node}(s)$ is a diagonal matrix in which elements are defined by the individual converter, source, and load small-signal admittance matrices,

$$\mathbf{Y}_{node}(s) = \text{blkdiag} \left[\mathbf{Y}_1(s) \cdots \mathbf{Y}_n(s) \quad \mathbf{Y}_{g1}(s) \cdots \mathbf{Y}_{gm}(s) \right]. \quad (2.5)$$

Combining Eq. (2.1) and Eq. (2.3) gives the multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) closed-loop representation of the energy hub,

$$\Delta \mathbf{V} = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{Z}_{edge}(s)\mathbf{Y}_{node}(s))^{-1} \mathbf{Z}_{edge}(s)\Delta \mathbf{I}_N, \quad (2.6)$$

which is depicted in Fig. 2.3. The loop gain matrix of the closed-loop system is then defined as:

$$\mathbf{L}(s) = \mathbf{Z}_{edge}(s)\mathbf{Y}_{node}(s). \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.3: MIMO closed-loop representation of hybrid AC/DC energy hub with node admittance and edge impedance matrix.

Similar to the classical source-load method, the small-signal stability of the energy hub is assessed by evaluating the Nyquist plot of $\mathbf{L}(s)$ and applying GNC to the loop gain matrix. This criterion states that a system is stable if and only if the eigenloci of $\mathbf{L}(s)$, taken together, encircle the $(-1, 0j)$ point P_l times counterclockwise in the Nyquist plot, assuming that there are no hidden unstable modes and with P_l the number of RHP poles of $\mathbf{L}(s)$ counting multiplicities [16]. The eigenloci are the eigenvalues of the loop gain matrix evaluated over the entire frequency range, i.e. $\lambda_i(\mathbf{L}(j\omega))$.

Since there is no aggregation of multiple converters in a single subsystem, adverse converter-related interactions within the subsystem are avoided. Furthermore, $\mathbf{Z}_{edge}(s)$ only consists of passive network elements, e.g. transmission lines, and the diagonal elements of $\mathbf{Y}_{node}(s)$ contain no RHP poles as the converters, sources and loads are assumed individually stable. Hence, $\mathbf{L}(s)$ has no RHP poles, i.e. $P_l = 0$. The energy hub is, therefore, stable if no eigenloci encircle the $(-1, 0j)$ point. Such a stability analysis enables the use of black-box models since the eigenloci can be plotted based on the frequency response data of $\mathbf{L}(s)$.

2.1.2 System oscillation mode and participation factor analysis

Equivalent to the eigenvalue analysis in the state-space framework, it is possible to determine the oscillation modes of the hybrid AC/DC energy hub based on the MIMO closed-loop representation developed in the previous section. These modes provide insights into the oscillatory behavior of the node voltages and the cause of possible system instability. The identification of oscillation modes in the impedance-based framework is done using the closed-loop bus impedance matrix, denoted by $\mathbf{Z}_{bus}^{cl}(s)$. This matrix gives the relation between the small-signal current disturbances at the nodes and resulting node voltage variations,

$$\Delta \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{Z}_{bus}^{cl}(s)\Delta \mathbf{I}_N, \quad (2.8)$$

and is calculated based on the closed-loop transfer function matrix provided in Eq. (2.6). The system oscillation modes are then determined by applying an eigenvalue decomposition (EVD) of $\mathbf{Z}_{bus}^{cl}(s)$ as explained in [17] for analyzing harmonic resonance modes in passive systems. It is important to note that, contrary to the eigenvalue analysis, the EVD is given by:

$$\mathbf{Z}_{bus}^{cl}(j\omega) = \mathbf{\Phi}(j\omega)\mathbf{\Lambda}(j\omega)\mathbf{\Psi}(j\omega), \quad (2.9)$$

where $\mathbf{\Lambda}(j\omega)$ is the diagonal eigenvalue matrix and $\mathbf{\Phi}(j\omega)$ and $\mathbf{\Psi}(j\omega)$ the right and left eigenvector matrices respectively. The main oscillation modes are then identified based on the peak absolute values of the eigenvalues $|\lambda_i(j\omega)|$ [17].

To gain additional insights into the cause of adverse interactions, the observability, controllability, and participation factors can be calculated for a particular oscillation mode. As explained in [18], the observability and

controllability of oscillation mode i with oscillation frequency ω_m at terminal k are respectively calculated from the eigenvectors of the EVD as:

$$O_{ki}(j\omega_m) = \frac{|\phi_{ki}(j\omega_m)|}{\sum_{k=1}^N |\phi_{ki}(j\omega_m)|}, \quad (2.10a)$$

$$C_{ki}(j\omega_m) = \frac{|\psi_{ik}(j\omega_m)|}{\sum_{k=1}^N |\psi_{ik}(j\omega_m)|}. \quad (2.10b)$$

The system locations where an oscillatory mode is more manifested can be obtained by the mode observability, whereas the mode controllability reveals the most influential nodes. In addition, the participation factors indicate the contribution of a terminal to an oscillation mode with frequency ω_m [19]:

$$P_{ki}(j\omega_m) = \frac{|\phi_{ki}(j\omega_m)\psi_{ik}(j\omega_m)|}{\sum_{k=1}^N |\phi_{ki}(j\omega_m)\psi_{ik}(j\omega_m)|}. \quad (2.11)$$

Contrary to the state-space framework, the contribution of particular control loops or passive network components to the oscillation modes cannot be determined via these participation factors. However, the benefit of this approach is that only frequency response data, i.e. no internal details of the system components, is needed to determine the participation factors of $\mathbf{Z}_{bus}^{cl}(j\omega)$. The participation factor analysis therefore identifies possible causes of instability while still being compatible with the black-box model representation of the energy hub.

2.2 Transmission Line Modeling

As the converter controllers are active over a wide frequency range, it becomes crucial to represent the frequency-dependent characteristics of transmission lines. This is especially true for cables, as given that a significant part of the energy hub lies offshore, the connection of most of the components will be done by means of subsea cables. Moreover, given the difficulty of installing new overhead lines onshore, it is highly likely that a large share of existing/future onshore transmission will also be based on underground cables. Hence, detailed cable models are necessary to investigate potential interactions between converter controllers and the impedance of the AC and/or DC networks.

For both overhead lines and cables, the two-port representation is obtained as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cosh(\Gamma l) & \mathbf{Y}_c^{-1} \sinh(\Gamma l) \\ \mathbf{Y}_c \sinh(\Gamma l) & \cosh(\Gamma l) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.12)$$

where $\Gamma = \sqrt{\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Y}}$, $\mathbf{Y}_c = \mathbf{Z}^{-1}\Gamma$ and l is the line length. \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Y} are the series impedance and shunt admittance, which are derived using distinct procedures for overhead lines and cables based on the exact geometry and configuration [11].

Even though using the same voltage rating for the onshore and offshore cables would lead to similar cable geometries, one significant difference between onshore and offshore cables is bundling. While onshore cables can be laid separately, offshore cables are commonly bundled in a single armour to reduce cable laying costs as depicted in Fig. 2.4. As investigated in detail in [20], a submarine cable enclosed in a pipe can be modeled using three single-phase conductors since each conductor has a separate metallic screen.

Figure 2.4: Onshore (left) and offshore (right) cable layouts in PSCAD.

2.3 Converter Modeling

Energy hubs are expected to contain a significant number of power electronic converters, thus their accurate modeling is of utmost importance for the analysis of potential converter interactions. The so-called multiple dq -frame model from [21] is used to accurately represent modular multilevel converters (MMCs) used in the HVDC links. The model takes into account the internal frequency couplings inside the converter and achieves a high modeling accuracy with a reasonable model order. By defining the inputs and outputs of the state-space model as $[\Delta v_k^{dc} \quad \Delta v_k^d \quad \Delta v_k^q]^T$ and $[\Delta i_k^{dc} \quad \Delta i_k^d \quad \Delta i_k^q]^T$, the 3×3 (dc, d, q) admittance matrix of MMC at node k is given by:

$$\Delta \mathbf{i}_k = \mathbf{Y}_{MMCk}(s) \Delta \mathbf{v}_k. \quad (2.13)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta i_k^{dc} \\ \Delta i_k^d \\ \Delta i_k^q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{MMC}^{dc,dc}(s) & Y_{MMC}^{dc,d}(s) & Y_{MMC}^{dc,q}(s) \\ Y_{MMC}^{d,dc}(s) & Y_{MMC}^{d,d}(s) & Y_{MMC}^{d,q}(s) \\ Y_{MMC}^{q,dc}(s) & Y_{MMC}^{q,d}(s) & Y_{MMC}^{q,q}(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta v_k^{dc} \\ \Delta v_k^d \\ \Delta v_k^q \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.14)$$

Within the impedance-based framework the converter models are evaluated at their local d, q reference frame, with q -axis lagging the d -axis. The rotation in Eq. (2.15) is therefore used to refer all admittance-based HVDC converter representations in their local (dc, d, q) reference frame to a global one [22]. The particular case for devices solely interfacing the AC network is obtained by removing the first column and row from Eq. (2.15). This step can be omitted for the interconnecting AC and DC networks as they are typically invariant with respect to the orientation of the frame [22].

$$\mathbf{R}(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix}, \quad \theta = \theta_{global} - \theta_{local}. \quad (2.15)$$

2.4 Offshore Wind Farm Modeling

As the integration of bulk renewable energy is a distinguishing aspect of energy hubs, accurate modeling of OWFs is crucial in small-signal stability studies for energy hubs. In this section a representative model is developed for a single Type IV wind turbine, whose ratings can be scaled up to represent an entire OWF. Following the introduction of the model, a simplified version is also developed, and the model simplification is justified.

2.4.1 Grid-Following Wind Turbine Model

The model description of a Type IV wind turbine is presented here, whose configuration is represented in Fig. 2.5.

The wind turbine is composed of a Grid-Side Converter (GSC), a Rotor-Side Converter (RSC), a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG), and its rotor. The converters are connected in a back-to-back setting,

Figure 2.5: Configuration of Wind Turbine Model.

and a DC capacitor is included in the DC link. The rotor is modeled using a multi-mass model, and doing so ensures that the model can capture the aerodynamic characteristics related to capturing wind energy.

The GSC is responsible for the DC voltage regulation while also utilizing a Phase Locked Loop (PLL) for synchronizing with the offshore collection network. The RSC is responsible for the regulation of torque applied to PMSG and it has a torque controller and a current controller.

Wind power output varies depending on wind velocity. This characteristic can be described as follows:

$$P_{wt}^* = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 C_p V_w^3 = k_o C_p V_w^3 \quad \& \quad \lambda = \frac{R \Omega_r}{V_w} \quad (2.16)$$

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = c_1 \left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_k} - c_3 \beta - c_4 \right) e^{-\frac{c_5}{\lambda_k}} + c_6 \lambda \quad (2.17)$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_k} = \frac{1}{\lambda + c_7 \beta} - \frac{c_8}{\beta^3 + 1} \quad (2.18)$$

where P_{wt} is power captured from rotor, V_w is wind velocity, R is blade radius, ρ is an air density, k_o is a rotor related constant, λ is tip speed ratio. C_p gives the rotor efficiency, where the polynomial coefficients c_1 - c_8 are taken as follows: $c_1 = 0.5176$, $c_2 = 116$, $c_3 = 0.4$, $c_4 = 5$, $c_5 = 21$, $c_6 = 0.0068$, $c_7 = 0.08$, $c_8 = 0.035$. In addition, it is assumed that the wind turbine is operated with a fine pitch angle (i.e., $\beta = 0$). More details about this wind turbine model can be found in [23].

The overall state-space model of the two converters are obtained as follows:

$$s \Delta \mathbf{x}_{GSC} = \mathbf{A}_{GSC} \Delta \mathbf{x}_{GSC} + \mathbf{B}_{GSC} \Delta \mathbf{u}_{GSC} \quad \& \quad s \Delta \mathbf{x}_{RSC} = \mathbf{A}_{RSC} \Delta \mathbf{x}_{RSC} + \mathbf{B}_{RSC} \Delta \mathbf{u}_{RSC} \quad (2.19)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{GSC} = [\mathbf{i}_{c,GSC}^{dq}, \varphi_{c,GSC}^{eq}, \varphi_{PLL}, \theta_{PLL}, \varphi_{dc}, \varphi_Q, u_{dc}]$ and $\mathbf{x}_{RSC} = [\varphi_{c,RSC}^{dq}, \varphi_t, \mathbf{i}_{c,RSC}^{dq}, \omega_r, \omega_g, \theta_{diff}]$. In this model the rotor-related dynamics and the PMSG model are included in the RSC model (using the state variables $\mathbf{i}_{c,RSC}^{dq}, \omega_r, \omega_g, \theta_{diff}$).

2.4.2 Simplified Wind Farm Model for System-Wide Stability Analysis

For impedance-based stability analysis from the network point-of-view, we can express the OWF topology and control structure using a 2×2 (d, q) admittance matrix of the OWF at node gk as follows:

$$\Delta \mathbf{i}_{gk} = \mathbf{Y}_{OWFk}(s) \Delta \mathbf{v}_{gk} \quad (2.20)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{i}_{gk}^d \\ \Delta \mathbf{i}_{gk}^q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{OWF}^{d,d}(s) & Y_{OWF}^{d,q}(s) \\ Y_{OWF}^{q,d}(s) & Y_{OWF}^{q,q}(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{v}_{gk}^d \\ \Delta \mathbf{v}_{gk}^q \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.21)$$

The simplification is based on the assumption that from a network point of view, the rotor-side dynamics can be excluded during small-signal stability analysis. The OWF model has three inputs which are wind velocity and the d- and q-axis components of the grid voltage. If the compensated voltage modulation technique is used,

perturbations from the AC grid that are reflected on the DC voltage are not propagated to the rotor side [24]. This modulation strategy compensates for DC voltage fluctuation, and it is described as follows:

$$\Delta m^{dq,*} = \Delta y^{dq} \frac{2}{\Delta v^{dc}}, \quad \Delta v_c^{dq} = \frac{\Delta v^{dc}}{2} \Delta m^{dq,*} \quad (2.22)$$

where Δy^{dq} is the output from controller (containing the voltage references), $\Delta m^{dq,*}$ is the modulation index of the converter and Δv_c^{dq} is the converter terminal voltage. Replacing one of the DC voltages in Eq. (2.22) with the nominal DC voltage would result in the uncompensated modulation strategy. Even though both the GSC and the RSC share the DC voltage and also utilize it for control with the fact that grid side perturbation is reflected on this voltage, the compensated modulation strategy prevents this fluctuation effect from appearing on the rotor side dynamics by assuming that every control process can be considered as flawless and conducted instantaneously.

The simplification is justified using both state-space-based and frequency-domain analysis. To show the effectiveness of our approach by state-space analysis, an open-loop OWF model is derived which has three inputs as described before.

$$s\Delta x_{OWF} = A_{OWF}\Delta x_{OWF} + B_{OWF}\Delta u_{OWF} \quad (2.23)$$

where $x_{OWF} = [i_{c,GSC}^{dq}, \varphi_{c,GSC}^{eq}, \varphi_{PLL}, \theta_{PLL}, \varphi_{dc}, \varphi_Q, u_{dc}, \varphi_{c,RSC}^{eq}, \varphi_t, i_{c,GSC}^{dq}, \omega_r, \omega_g, \theta_{diff}]$. and $u_{OWF} = [u_{pcc}^{dq}, V_w]$. We can evaluate the connectivity between sub-systems inside the OWF model, whose system matrix contains two distinct parts related to the GSC and the RSC. This evaluation result is represented in Fig. 2.6, which shows the sparsity patterns of the OWF model system matrix.

Figure 2.6: Sparsity patterns of the OWF model system matrix for different modulation schemes.

The effectiveness of the compensated modulation strategy in decoupling the rotor-side dynamics is evident in Fig. 2.6: with compensated modulation, there is no connectivity from RS dynamics to GS dynamics through the coupling state DC voltage u_{dc} (the column for the state variable at index 9 is empty at the lower left sub-matrix). Interactions can only propagate from RS dynamics to GS dynamics when the uncompensated modulation strategy is used, as indicated by the blue crosses in the lower left sub-matrix. Therefore, if the compensated modulation is chosen, GS-related dynamics could be only reflected on the network, and RS dynamics cannot be identified through GS perturbations.

To provide more evidence for strengthening our simplification, a comparison of frequency domain response is carried out between two models: a model featuring only the GSC, and another one including the entire wind turbine model. The results of this comparison are shown in Fig. 2.7.

Fig. 2.7 shows that there are negligible differences between the dq -frame admittances obtained from the two models, showing that when compensated modulation strategy is adopted the rotor-side dynamics can be excluded. If the uncompensated modulation strategy is adopted, this difference would highly depend on the dc-side capacitor, meaning that a smaller capacitance value would result in a higher reflection of the RS dynamics upon perturbation at GS.

Figure 2.7: Frequency domain response comparison results between GSC-only and wind turbine model.

It is worth noting that this simplified approach is only valid for a generic grid-following wind farm model and when the rotor-side dynamics are stable by themselves. Specifically, without any control modification from the above description e.g., frequency support control with OWF. Moreover, this simplification will also not be valid when the OWF is equipped with grid-forming control.

2.5 Automated Subsystem Identification in the Frequency Domain

In order to carry out stability studies in the frequency domain, it is essential to obtain detailed component representations. In the availability of analytical models, the terminal characteristics of active and passive devices can be obtained in a straightforward manner. This, however, is usually not applicable in real-life projects due to the difficulty of developing accurate analytical models. More importantly, the IP concerns of the equipment vendors come into the picture when power electronic converters are considered, which strongly limits the amount of available information on component models. Despite recent efforts towards open control structures in HVDC systems [25], the lower-level control—which significantly shapes the converter dynamic behavior at relatively high frequencies—is still mostly considered to be confidential, limiting the extent to which extensive stability studies can be carried out by system operators.

In the absence of detailed analytical models, black-boxed component models become useful alternatives for stability analysis. Detailed black-box models can be provided by converter vendors in EMT software, which can be used by system operators for stability studies. In contrast to time-consuming time-domain studies, in an impedance-based framework, the device terminal characteristics can be represented using impedance/admittance transfer functions calculated at a certain operating point, and eventually, conclusions on system stability can be obtained. However, the procedure to obtain impedance/admittance transfer functions from black-boxed EMT models of power electronic converters is often a lengthy manual process rendering the stability analysis less efficient.

Given the importance of black-box models in the stability analysis of energy hubs, an automated frequency domain frequency scanning tool is developed in Python and PSCAD. The tool is provided as a PSCAD library and a set of Python scripts, and automates the calculation of impedance/admittance transfer functions by carrying out frequency sweeps using parallel simulations. This automation significantly improves the efficiency of the process of determining the terminal characteristics of black-box models, and is explained in detail in the upcoming sections.

2.5.1 Generalities of the identification procedure

The stability analysis described in Section 2.1 relies on the open-loop admittance of the selected subsystem. Therefore, said subsystems need to be decoupled at their terminals. This is achieved by connecting controlled shunt voltage sources as illustrated in Fig. 2.8. For this decoupling to be effective, the voltage sources need to be ideal, i.e. they present zero impedance and are controlled to reproduce the steady-state fundamental frequency voltage waveform. Therefore, the operating point of each subsystem is unaltered, which is of importance for devices whose characteristics change with the operating point, e.g. HVDC converters. After the decoupling takes place, a snapshot can be taken to resume subsequent simulations avoiding the initialization transient.

Figure 2.8: MMC station identification example in PSCAD.

The computation of each admittance matrix—at the AC or DC side of converters—is based on the application of ordinary least squares considering that in an M -dimensional space, a linearly independent set can have at most M vectors. For instance, $M = 2$ in the d,q frame for AC sources/loads, whereas $M = 3$ in the dc,d,q frame for HVDC converters. Therefore, every subsystem is excited at a given frequency as many times as degrees of freedom for its chosen representation. This is performed in parallel for improved efficiency. After each subsystem reaches a sinusoidal steady state, the single-sided FFT is applied to the recorded small-signal currents and voltages. The frequency-domain currents and voltages at the target frequency are retrieved for each perturbation frequency, which are then used to compute the admittance matrix. The aforementioned procedure can be summarised in the following steps:

1. Initializing run to obtain steady-state values
2. Decoupling by ideal sources keeping the operating point
3. Snapshot: states are recorded to initialize future runs
4. Sinusoidal voltage perturbation for every frequency of interest and each degree of freedom
5. Record sinusoidal steady-state response and apply FFT

The previous process is illustrated in Fig. 2.9 on the d -axis voltage of a single MMC station¹. The voltage perturbation at 200 Hz results in one of the three independent voltage perturbation sets and associated currents. The time axis is purposely left blank as the time separation between the different steps is intentionally increased for illustration purposes.

In the following, Sections 2.5.2 and 2.5.3 delve into the identification of sources/loads and converters, respectively, which is key to construct the node admittance matrix $\mathbf{Y}_{node}(s)$. In addition, Section 2.5.4 introduces the proposed approach to characterize the AC and DC transmission networks interconnecting sources, loads, and converters, which is used to compute the edge impedance matrix $\mathbf{Z}_{edge}(s)$.

¹The steady-state periodicity is no longer reflected at the terminal voltage after the ideal voltage source is connected. However, note that the inherent periodicity of the MMC is still preserved.

Figure 2.9: Illustration of a single-frequency perturbation.

2.5.2 Admittance identification of sources and loads

The particularity of the sources/loads identification procedure is that they are interfaced to the system by a single AC three-phase connection point, i.e., each source/load is connected to a single bus. As AC sources/loads are represented in the d,q frame, two linearly independent sets of small-signal voltage perturbations at a given frequency $s = j\omega$ are applied while the currents are recorded. Once a sinusoidal steady state is reached, single-sided FFT is applied to the small-signal currents and voltages, and the values at the target frequency are retrieved. Finally, the admittance in the dq -reference frame of the scan block is given by Eq. (2.24):

$$\mathbf{Y}_{dq}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta i_1^d(s) & \Delta i_2^d(s) \\ \Delta i_1^q(s) & \Delta i_2^q(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta v_1^d(s) & \Delta v_2^d(s) \\ \Delta v_1^q(s) & \Delta v_2^q(s) \end{bmatrix}^{-1}, \quad (2.24)$$

where the sub-indices 1 and 2 refer to the values obtained for each linearly independent set of perturbations. For simplicity, the implementation performs a perturbation in the d -axis voltage while the q -axis voltage is kept constant, which corresponds to the first independent set, and a voltage perturbation in the q -axis while the d -axis voltage is kept constant which corresponds to the second independent set.

2.5.3 Admittance identification of converters

The identification of converters is similar to that of sources/loads, except the converters are also interfaced to the system by a DC port. Therefore, in order to obtain the corresponding 3×3 admittance matrix, three linearly independent sets of voltage perturbations are applied: two at the AC side and one at the DC side, while all currents are recorded. Consequently, the admittance in the dq -reference frame of the converter's scan block can be computed by Eq. (2.25):

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y^{dc,dc}(s) & Y^{dc,d}(s) & Y^{dc,q}(s) \\ Y^{d,dc}(s) & Y^{d,d}(s) & Y^{d,q}(s) \\ Y^{q,dc}(s) & Y^{q,d}(s) & Y^{q,q}(s) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta i_1^{dc}(s) & \Delta i_2^{dc}(s) & \Delta i_3^{dc}(s) \\ \Delta i_1^d(s) & \Delta i_2^d(s) & \Delta i_3^d(s) \\ \Delta i_1^q(s) & \Delta i_2^q(s) & \Delta i_3^q(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta v_1^{dc}(s) & \Delta v_2^{dc}(s) & \Delta v_3^{dc}(s) \\ \Delta v_1^d(s) & \Delta v_2^d(s) & \Delta v_3^d(s) \\ \Delta v_1^q(s) & \Delta v_2^q(s) & \Delta v_3^q(s) \end{bmatrix}^{-1}. \quad (2.25)$$

The sub-indices refer to the values computed for each linearly independent set of perturbations, which are practically implemented as separated d , q and dc voltage perturbations, e.g. while applying the small-signal dc voltage perturbation, the d and q voltages are kept unchanged.

2.5.4 Admittance identification of AC and DC networks

The goal of the network characterization is to compute the edge admittance matrix at each angular frequency, $\mathbf{Y}_{edge}(s)$. Since the frequency domain characterization for AC and DC networks solely differs in the dimensionality of each representation, i.e. two dimensions for the three-phase AC network (d,q) and one for the DC network (dc),

and in the fundamental frequency, only the case of DC transmission network identification is explained in detail hereafter.

Considering an arbitrary N -bus DC network, the edge admittance matrix relating each node's voltages and currents would be of size $N \times N$. Therefore, N linearly independent voltage perturbation sets are carried out at each frequency, noted by the sub-index $1, \dots, N$. After reaching a sinusoidal steady state, single-sided FFT is applied to retrieve the target frequency response from the small-signal currents and voltages measured at every node, noted by the super-index I, \dots, N . Lastly, the $N \times N$ admittance matrix at each angular frequency is computed by Eq. (2.26).

$$\mathbf{Y}_{edge}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta i_1^I & \dots & \Delta i_N^I \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Delta i_1^N & \dots & \Delta i_N^N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta v_1^I & \dots & \Delta v_N^I \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Delta v_1^N & \dots & \Delta v_N^N \end{bmatrix}^{-1}. \quad (2.26)$$

Each scanning block allows for an independent perturbation of the network, while the topology information is used to select the involved perturbation blocks and to record only the target currents and voltages. Lastly, the extension of Eq. (2.26) for AC network identification is achieved by noting that the dimensionality is doubled because the dynamics of a balanced three-phase system are represented in the dq reference frame.

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter discussed the modeling of energy hubs. The impedance-based stability analysis was introduced, and its suitability for stability analysis in the presence of black-box component models was discussed. Model development guidelines were given for main energy hub elements such as subsea cables, converters and offshore wind farms. Finally, an automated frequency scanning toolbox was introduced, which can help obtaining black-box component models using detailed EMT models.

Bibliography

- [1] M. Geidl, G. Koepfel, P. Favre-Perrod, B. Klockl, G. Andersson, and K. Frohlich, "Energy hubs for the future," *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 24–30, 2007.
- [2] M. Mohammadi, Y. Noorollahi, B. Mohammadi-ivatloo, and H. Yousefi, "Energy hub: From a model to a concept – a review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 80, pp. 1512–1527, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032117310985>
- [3] N. Cutululis, F. Blaabjerg, J. Østergaard, C. Bak, M. Anderson, F. Silva, H. Johansson, X. Wang, and B. Jørgensen, "The Energy Islands: A Mars Mission for the Energy system," Aalborg University and DTU, Tech. Rep., 2021.
- [4] "Key Concepts, howpublished = <https://northseawindpowerhub.eu/key-concepts>, note = Last accessed: Oct. 25, 2023."
- [5] R. Rosso, X. Wang, M. Liserre, X. Lu, and S. Engelken, "Grid-forming converters: Control approaches, grid-synchronization, and future trends—a review," *IEEE Open Journal of Industry Applications*, vol. 2, pp. 93–109, 2021.
- [6] J. Matevosyan, B. Badrzadeh, T. Prevost, E. Quitmann, D. Ramasubramanian, H. Urdal, S. Achilles, J. MacDowell, S. H. Huang, V. Vital, J. O'Sullivan, and R. Quint, "Grid-forming inverters: Are they the key for high renewable penetration?" *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 89–98, 2019.
- [7] L. Zhang, L. Harnefors, and H.-P. Nee, "Power-synchronization control of grid-connected voltage-source converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 809–820, 2010.
- [8] M. Chandorkar, D. Divan, and R. Adapa, "Control of parallel connected inverters in standalone ac supply systems," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 136–143, 1993.
- [9] S. D'Arco and J. A. Suul, "Equivalence of virtual synchronous machines and frequency-droops for converter-based microgrids," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 394–395, 2014.
- [10] —, "Virtual synchronous machines — classification of implementations and analysis of equivalence to droop controllers for microgrids," in *2013 IEEE Grenoble Conference*, 2013, pp. 1–7.
- [11] A. Lekić and J. Beerten, "Generalized multiport representation of power systems using ABCD parameters for harmonic stability analysis," *Proc. Electric Power System Research: Proceedings of the 21st Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC 2020)*, vol. 189, 2020, 7 pages.
- [12] M. Amin and M. Molinas, "Small-signal stability assessment of power electronics based power systems: A discussion of impedance- and eigenvalue-based methods," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 5014–5030, Sep. 2017.
- [13] C. Desoer and Y.-T. Wang, "On the generalized nyquist stability criterion," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 187–196, 1980.

- [14] T. Roose, A. Lekić, M. M. Alam, and J. Beerten, "Stability analysis of high-frequency interactions between a converter and HVDC grid resonances," *IEEE Trans. Power Deliv.*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 3414–3425, Dec. 2021.
- [15] J. Pedra, L. Sainz, and L. Monjo, "Three-port small signal admittance-based model of VSCs for studies of multi-terminal HVDC hybrid AC/DC transmission grids," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 732–743, Jan. 2021.
- [16] J. Maciejowski, *Multivariable feedback design*, 1st ed. Wokingham, UK: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, 1989.
- [17] W. Xu, Z. Huang, Y. Cui, and H. Wang, "Harmonic resonance mode analysis," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1182 – 1190, Apr. 2005.
- [18] Y. Zhan, X. Xie, and Y. Wang, "Impedance network model based modal observability and controllability analysis for renewable integrated power systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Deliv.*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 2025–2034, Aug. 2021.
- [19] E. Ebrahimzadeh, F. Blaabjerg, X. Wang, and C. L. Bak, "Bus participation factor analysis for harmonic instability in power electronics based power systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 33, no. 12, pp. 10341–10351, Dec. 2018.
- [20] C. Jensen, F. F. da Silva, C. Bak, and W. Wiechowski, "Switching studies for the Horns Rev 2 wind farm main cable," in *Proc. 2011 International Conference on Power System Transients (IPST)*, 2011, 7 pages.
- [21] G. Bergna-Diaz, J. Freytes, X. Guillaud, S. D'Arco, and J. A. Suul, "Generalized voltage-based state-space modeling of modular multilevel converters with constant equilibrium in steady state," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 707–725, 2018.
- [22] C. Zhang, M. Molinas, A. Rygg, and X. Cai, "Impedance-based analysis of interconnected power electronics systems: Impedance network modeling and comparative studies of stability criteria," *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Top. Power Electron.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 2520–2533, Sep. 2020.
- [23] T. Burton, N. Jenkins, D. Sharpe, and E. Bossanyi, *Wind Energy Handbook*, 1st ed. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2011.
- [24] A. Yazdani and R. Iravani, *Voltage-Sourced Converters in Power Systems: Modeling, Control, and Applications*, 1st ed. Wiley-IEEE Press, 2010.
- [25] I. Jahn, L. Bessegato, J. Björk, F. Hohn, S. Norrga, N. Svensson, K. Sharifabadi, and O. Despuys, "A proposal for open-source HVDC control," in *Proc. 2019 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Europe (ISGT-Europe)*, 2019, 5 pages.